

Knowledge, Attitude and Perception On Anaemia in Pregnancy Among Pregnant Women in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Anaemia is one of the most common nutritional deficiency illnesses and a global public health problem that affects both developing and industrialized countries, with severe implications for human health as well as social and economic development. The iron deficiency anaemia is one of the most shared type of anaemia which would regularly affect women of procreative age group, particularly pregnant women. The study investigated the knowledge, attitude and perception on anaemia in pregnancy among pregnant women in Ojo local government area Lagos state. A cross sectional study was conducted among pregnant women in Ojo local government, Lagos state. The assessment of the knowledge, attitude and perception on anaemia in pregnancy was done using questionnaire as the method of data collection. Three hundred completely filled responses were retrieved. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 was used in analysing the collected data so as to generate frequency, tables under the branch of descriptive statistics. The study revealed that 228(76%) of the respondents are aware of anaemia in pregnancy. Among the 228 respondents who are aware of anaemia in pregnancy, 143(62.7%) got the information from health Centre, 14(6.1%) got it from a friend, 71(31.2%) got it from the internet. Hence, most of the respondent heard about anaemia in pregnancy from the health Centre. 152(50.7%), agreed that regular antenatal check-up of blood tests are essential during pregnancy. However, majority of the respondents are aware of anaemia in pregnancy. Findings from this

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study revealed that respondents have a good knowledge on anaemia including the signs and symptoms associated with it. It was recommended among others that educative materials, posters and leaflets on anaemia prevention should be made available to convey messages on the dangers of anaemia especially in pregnancy.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Perception, Anaemia, Pregnancy,

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Introduction

Over the years the study on anaemia increased as it has been discovered to be a mutual health challenge for pregnant women mostly in developing countries. According to a study published by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2020, anaemia afflicted 1.62 billion (24.8 percent) of the world's population (WHO, 2020). Anaemia was estimated to affect about 51% of pregnant women. Numerous studies have described anaemia as a condition in which the amount of haemoglobin (Hb) or red blood cells is lower than the normal value. This is a circumstance when the amount of red blood cells or the oxygen carrying ability of those cells are inadequate to satisfy bodily demands. The most common form of anaemia, iron deficiency anaemia, is caused by a lack of iron intake or absorption, as well as excessive iron loss (Soundarya, 2016). Anaemia can exist in two forms symptomatic or asymptomatic. Being dizzy, tremor and easy fatigue are some of the symptoms a person can display when having anaemia.

Anaemia is responsible for nearly 120,000 maternal deaths worldwide, accounting for nearly a fifth (18%) of all maternal deaths. Pregnancy anaemia is now a serious public health issue, predominantly in developing countries (Alem, et al, 2013). Some studies have found that anaemia is now a major cause of maternal death, especially in developing countries, where there is a clear link between severe anaemia and maternal mortality. Anaemia is harmful to both mothers and fetuses during pregnancy, raising maternal and perinatal mortality and placing babies at risk for long-term cognitive damage.

Anaemia has been linked to slowed brain growth as well as long-term behavioral and cognitive decline (Muriuki & Mentzer, 2020) Despite its negative health consequences, the true burden in African children is uncertain due to the diverse associations of biochemical markers with inflammation and infections such as malaria (Muriuki & Mentzer, 2020). In most developing countries, anaemia is four times more common than in developed countries. In less developed countries, anaemia affects more than half of pregnant women (World Health Organization, 2020) as women who are pregnant are affected in all the trimesters of pregnancy. The study is aimed to determine the knowledge, attitude and perception of pregnant women on anaemia in pregnancy in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos State. This study specifically:

1. determined the knowledge of the respondent on anaemia during pregnancy;
2. assessed the perception of the respondent regarding the predisposing risks factors associated with anaemia during pregnancy; and
3. examined the attitude of the respondent towards anaemia during pregnancy.

Research Questions

The study provided answers to the following questions:

1. What is the knowledge of the respondent on anaemia during pregnancy?
2. What is the perception of the respondent regarding the predisposing risks factors associated with anaemia during pregnancy?
3. What is the attitude of the respondent towards anaemia during pregnancy?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for this study.

1. Socio demographic variables do not significantly influence respondent knowledge on anaemia in pregnancy.
2. Socio demographic variables do not significantly influence respondent perception on anaemia in pregnancy.

3. Socio demographic variables do not significantly influence respondent attitude on anaemia in pregnancy

Methodology

A descriptive cross sectional survey design was adopted in this study to evaluate pregnant women's knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions about anaemia during pregnancy. The study population used for this research will include the pregnant women attending the Primary Health Centres in Ojo Local Government Area. The study adopted the convenient sampling technique to select 300 respondents, that is, whosoever attended the health centre antenatal clinic at the selected health facilities on the day of the distribution, until the sample size is reached, were considered.

The research instrument was self-designed by the researcher which consisted of four sections A – D. The face and content validity of the instrument was established by experts in the field of Nursing Science. Descriptive statistics such as frequency count and percentage was used to answer the research questions while multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the knowledge of the respondent on anaemia during pregnancy?

Table 1: Knowledge of Anaemia in pregnancy

Variables	YES {%}	NO {%}	I DON'T KNOW {%}
1. Anaemia is a decrease in concentration of red blood cells?	129 {43.0}	9 {3.0}	162 {54.0}
2. Do you belief anaemia in pregnancy is a serious health challenge?	143{47.7 }	25{8.3 }	132{44.0 }
3. Do you know that anaemia can affect pregnancy?	151{50.3 }	23{7.7 }	126{42.0 }
4. Being a sickle cell patient puts you at risk of anaemia in pregnancy?	130{43.3 }	16{5.3 }	153{51.0 }
5. When a pregnant woman does not eat nutritious meal, she is at risk of anaemia in pregnancy?	161{53.7 }	14{4.7 }	125{41.7 }
6. Can anaemia in pregnancy affect both mother and child?	88{29.3 }	32{18.7 }	180{60.0 }
7. Does the intake of vitamin B12 helps in preventing anaemia?	103{34.3 }	19{6.3 }	178{59.3 }
8. Does having two closely spaced pregnancies put you at risk of anaemia in pregnancy?	3{1.0 }	85{28.3 }	188{62.7 }
9. Is a woman at risk of anaemia if pregnant with twins?	79{26.3 }	27{9.0 }	194{64.7 }
10. When a woman does not consume enough iron, she is at risk of anaemia in pregnancy?	177{59.0 }	13{4.3 }	110{36.7 }

Table 1 revealed the respondent knowledge level of anaemia in pregnancy. From the table it could be deduced that most of the respondents are of the view that they do not know

if Anaemia is a decrease in concentration of red blood cells [Yes= 129(43%); No-9(3%); Don't know- 162(54%)]. Most of the respondents believe anaemia in pregnancy is a serious health challenge [Yes= 143(47.7%); No-25(8.3%); Don't know- 132 (44%)] and they also know that that anaemia can affect pregnancy [Yes= 151(50.3%); No-23(7.7%); Don't know- 126(42%)]. Most of them do not, however, know having a sickle cell patient puts one at risk of anaemia in pregnancy [Yes= 130(43.3%); No-16(5.3%); Don't know- 153(51%)]. Majority of the respondents believe that when a pregnant woman does not eat nutritious meal, she is at risk of anaemia in pregnancy [Yes= 161(53.7%); No-14(4.7%); Don't know- 125(41.7%)]. It could also be revealed from the table that majority of the respondents do not know if anaemia in pregnancy can affect both mother and child [Yes= 88(29.3%); No-32(18.7%); Don't know- 180(60%)]. and do not also if the intake of vitamin B12 helps in preventing anaemia [Yes= 103(19%); No-19(6.3%); Don't know- 178(59.3%)], do not also if having two closely spaced pregnancies can put one at risk of anaemia in pregnancy [Yes= 3(1%); No-85(28.3%); Don't know- 188(62.7%)], majority do not know if a woman is at risk of anaemia if pregnant with twins [Yes= 79(26.3%); No-27(9%); Don't know- 194(64.7%)]. But most of the respondents know that when a woman does not consume enough iron, she is at risk of anaemia in pregnancy [Yes= 79(26.3%); No-27(9%); don't know- 194(64.7%)]

Research Question 2: What is the perception of the respondent regarding the predisposing risks factors associated with anaemia during pregnancy?

Table 2: Perception on Anaemia in Pregnancy

S/N	QUESTIONS	A	D
1.	Tiredness and weakness are symptoms of anaemia?	123(41)	177(59)
2.	Does malaria in pregnancy result in anaemia in pregnancy?	106(35.3)	194(64.7)
3.	Worm infection can cause anaemia?	83(27.7%)	217(72.3)
4.	Inadequate intake of iron in diet during pregnancy can cause anaemia?	184(61.3)	116(38.6)
5.	Intake of diet rich in iron during pregnancy can prevent anaemia?	191(63.7)	109(36.7)
6.	Iron deficiency anaemia is considered to be dangerous during pregnancy?	181(60.3)	119(39.7)
7.	Pale face or tongue is a sign of anaemia?	95(31.7)	205(68.3)

Table 2 revealed the respondents' perception on anaemia in pregnancy. The table indicated that most of the respondents, 177(59%), disagreed that tiredness and weakness are symptoms of anaemia, while 123(41%) agreed. It was also revealed that majority of the respondents, 194(64.7%) disagreed that malaria in pregnancy result in anaemia in pregnancy and most of them, 217(72.3), were of the opinion that worm infection can not cause anaemia, while 83(27.7%) disagreed. It could be presumed from the table that most of the respondents, 184(61.3%), agreed that Inadequate intake of iron in diet during pregnancy can cause anaemia, 116 (38.6%) disagreed and they mostly, 191(63.7%), agreed that Intake of diet rich in iron during pregnancy can prevent anaemia, while 109(36.7%) disagreed, most of them, agreed that Iron deficiency anaemia is considered to be dangerous during pregnancy, while 119(39.7%) disagreed, majority of the respondents, 205(68.3%), disagreed that Pale face or tongue is a sign of anaemia, while 95(31.7%) agreed.

Research Question 3: What is the attitude of the respondent towards anaemia during pregnancy?

Table 3: Attitude on Anaemia in Pregnancy

S/N	QUESTIONS	A	D
1.	Regular antenatal check-up of blood tests are essential during pregnancy	152(50.7)	148(49.3)
2.	Does receiving iron supplement in pregnancy prevent anaemia in pregnancy?	160(53.3)	140(46.7)
3.	Intake of folic acid can help reduce the risk of anaemia in pregnancy?	176(58.7)	124(41.3)
4.	Does the type of meal a woman consume result in anaemia in pregnancy?	112(37.3)	188(62.7)
5.	Will eating vegetables reduce the risk of anaemia in pregnancy?	108(36)	192(64)
6.	Spacing of pregnancies can help prevent anaemia in pregnancy?	98(32.7)	202(67.3)
7.	Pregnant women should take iron pills to prevent anaemia?	192(65.3)	108(34.7)
8.	Intake of citrus fruits such as lemon can help with absorption of iron?	185(61.7)	115(38.2)

Table 3 revealed the respondents attitude on anaemia in pregnancy. The table indicated that majority of the respondents, 152(50.7%), agreed that regular antenatal check-up of blood tests are essential during pregnancy, while 148(49.3%) disagreed. It was also indicated that most of the respondents, 160(53.3%) agreed that receiving iron supplement in pregnancy prevent anaemia in pregnancy, while 140(46.7%) disagreed. Most of the respondents, 176(58.7%), agreed that Intake of folic acid can help reduce the risk of anaemia in pregnancy, while 124(41.3) disagreed. However, most of the respondents, 188(62.7%), disagreed that the type of meal a woman consume result in anaemia in pregnancy, while 112(37.3%) disagreed. The table showed that majority of the respondents, 192(64%), disagreed that eating vegetables reduce the risk of anaemia in pregnancy, while 108(36%) disagreed. most of them, 202(67.3%), also disagreed that spacing of pregnancies can help prevent anaemia in pregnancy, 98(32.7%) agreed. It could be presumed from that table that most of the respondents, 192(65.3%), agreed that Pregnant women should take iron pills to prevent anaemia, while 108(34%) disagreed. 185(61.7%) of the respondent agreed that the intake of citrus fruits such as lemon can help with absorption of iron, while 115(38.2%) disagreed.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀1: Socio demographic variables do not significantly influence respondent knowledge on anaemia in pregnancy.

Table 4: Summary of multiple regression on the effect of socio-demographic influence on knowledge on anaemia in pregnancy

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	22.215	2.080		10.679	.000
Age	-.028	.062	-.028	-.449	.654
Marital Status	2.627	1.188	.138	2.212	.028
Ethnicity	-.066	.962	-.004	-.069	.945
Religion	1.252	1.015	.075	1.233	.219
Level Of Education	3.067	2.089	.091	1.468	.143
No Of Previous Pregnancy	.026	.396	.004	.067	.947

R= .149; R2= .022; Adj. R2= .002; Std. Error= 8.04165; F= 1.104; P>.05

Dependent Variable: Knowledge

Table 4 revealed that age has no significant influence on the knowledge on anaemia in pregnancy (Beta=-0.28; t=-.449; P>.05), marital status has a significant influence on knowledge on anaemia in pregnancy (Beta= .138; t= 2.212; P<.05), ethnicity (Beta=-.004; t=-.069; P>.05), religion (Beta= .075; t= 1.233; P>.05), level of education religion (Beta= .091; t= 1.468; P>.05), and number of previous (Beta= .004; t= .067; P>.05) have no individual significant influence on knowledge on anamia on pregnancy. Hence, it could be deduced from the analysis that among all the stated socio- demography, only marital status has a significant influence on knowledge on anaemia in pregnancy

H₀2: Socio demographic variables do not significantly influence respondent perception on anaemia in pregnancy.

Table 5: Summary of multiple regression on the effect of socio-demographic influence on perception on anaemia in pregnancy.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	19.941	1.439		13.860	.000
Age	.036	.043	.053	.837	.404
Marital Status	1.810	.821	.136	2.203	.028
Ethnicity	.342	.665	.030	.515	.607
Religion	-.022	.702	-.002	-.031	.975
Level Of Education	-1.670	1.445	-.071	-1.156	.249
No Of Previous Pregnancy	-.373	.274	-.088	-1.364	.174

R=0.172; R2= .030; Adj. R2= .010; Std. Error= 5.56184; F= 1.489; P>.05

Dependent Variable: Perception

Table 5 revealed that age has no significant influence on the respondents perception on anaemia in pregnancy (Beta=.053; t= .837; P>.05), marital status has a significant influence on perception on anaemia in pregnancy (Beta= .136; t= 2.203; P<.05), ethnicity (Beta=-.030; t=-.515; P>.05), religion (Beta= -.002; t= -.031; P>.05), level of education religion (Beta= -.071; t=

-1.156; $P > .05$), and number of previous pregnancy (Beta= -.088 ; $t = -1.364$; $P > .05$) have no individual significant influence on perception on anaemia on pregnancy. Hence, it could also be deduced from the analysis that among all the stated socio- demography, only marital status has a significant influence on perception on anaemia in pregnancy.

H₀₃: Socio demographic variables do not significantly influence respondent attitude on anaemia in pregnancy

Table 6: Summary of multiple regression on the effect of socio-demographic influence on attitude on anaemia in pregnancy.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	22.947	1.722		13.327	.000
Age	.056	.051	.068	1.088	.277
Marital Status	2.262	.983	.142	2.301	.022
Ethnicity	.644	.796	.048	.810	.419
Religion	-.563	.840	-.040	-.670	.503
Level Of Education	-3.439	1.729	-.122	-1.989	.048
No Of Previous Pregnancy	-.090	.327	-.018	-.276	.783

R=0.175; R²= .031; Adj. R²= .011; Std. Error= 6.65639; F= 1.542; $P > .05$

Dependent Variable: Attitude

Table 6 revealed that age has no significant influence on the attitude on anaemia in pregnancy (Beta=.053; $t = .837$; $P > .05$), marital status has a significant influence on attitude on anaemia in pregnancy (Beta= .142; $t = 2.301$; $P < .05$), ethnicity (Beta=-.048; $t = -.810$; $P > .05$), religion (Beta= -.563; $t = -.670$; $P > .05$), and number of previous pregnancy (Beta= -.018 ; $t = -.276$; $P > .05$) have no individual significant influence on attitude on anaemia on pregnancy. Level of education religion (Beta= -.122; $t = -1.989$; $P < .05$) has a significant influence on the attitude of the respondents on anaemia pregnancy. Hence, it could also be deduced from the analysis that among all the stated socio- demography, only marital status and level of education have significant influence on perception on anaemia in pregnancy

Discussion

Findings from this study revealed that (76%) of the respondents are aware of anaemia and 62.7% of the respondents got the information on anaemia from health centre, The result of this study is higher compared to the result gotten from the study of Nivedita and Shanthini (2016) which was conducted in India, where just 39.87% of the respondents were aware of and recognized the word anaemia whereas, in contrast to this study, Chacko et al., (2016) revealed that 50% of the respondents knowledge and understanding of anaemia is significantly poor, which may be attributed to the cause of pregnancy-related problems. More also, result showed that 43% of the respondents are of the view that they do not know if Anaemia is a decrease in concentration of red blood. Furthermore, result also revealed that 47% of the respondents believe anaemia in pregnancy is a serious health challenge and 50.3% also know that that anaemia can affect pregnancy as well as the unborn baby. This result is in line with the findings of Nivedita and Shanthini (2016) where 66.1% of the respondents agrees that extreme anaemia would affect the fetus. 53.7% of the respondent believe that when a pregnant woman does not eat nutritious meal, she is at risk of anaemia in

pregnancy. Result also revealed that 60% of the respondents do not know if anaemia in pregnancy can affect both mother and child.

Result revealed that most of the respondents, 177(59%), disagreed that tiredness and weakness are symptoms of anaemia. It was also revealed that (64.7%) of the respondents disagreed that malaria in pregnancy result in anaemia in pregnancy while 217(72.3) were of the opinion that worm infection can not cause anaemia. More also, 184(61.3%), agreed that Inadequate intake of iron in diet during pregnancy can cause anaemia, and 191(63.7%), agreed that Intake of diet rich in iron during pregnancy can prevent anaemia. This result agrees with the study of Soundarya (2016), which suggests that eating the right amount of food rich in Iron, copper, zinc, folic acid, Vitamin B-12, and protein-rich diets helps in the production of haemoglobin which in turns prevents anaemia.

Findings from this study revealed 50.7% agreed that regular antenatal check-up of blood tests are essential during pregnancy while (53.3%) agreed that receiving iron supplement in pregnancy prevent anaemia in pregnancy. Result also revealed that (58.7%) of the respondents' agreed that Intake of folic acid can help reduce the risk of anaemia in pregnancy, which supports the findings of Qureshi et al (2014) and Nivedita and Shanthini (2016) that says that 74.36% took iron supplements on a regular basis. Lastly, 65.3% of the respondents agreed that Pregnant women should take iron pills to prevent anaemia and (61.7%) of the respondent agreed that the intake of citrus fruits such as lemon can help with absorption of iron.

Conclusion and Recommendation

From the findings of this study, it could be concluded that respondents have good knowledge of, good perception of and positive attitude towards anaemia in pregnancy among pregnant women. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that;

1. Health education intervention by health care workers will increase the knowledge of pregnant women attending antenatal on the benefits of eating a healthy diet so as to prevent anaemia.
2. Government should also make a policy on iron deficiency prevention, so as to prevent anaemia in pregnancy.
3. Educative materials, posters and leaflets on anaemia prevention should be made available to convey messages on the dangers of anaemia especially in pregnancy.

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